

A STUDY ON CHILD ABUSE AND ITS AWARENESS

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Abstract:

Child abuse is physical, mental and psychological maltreatment that occurs in our society. The term child abuse is often interchangeably, although some researchers make a distinction between them, treating to cover neglect, exploitation, and trafficking. In this study it is helpful to control all the problems which is faced by the children both male and female in our society. The whole of recorded history contains references to acts that can be described as child abuse or child maltreatment, but professional inquiry into the topic is generally considered to have begun in the 1960s. Definitions of child maltreatment can vary across the sectors of society which deal with the issue, such as child protection agencies, legal and medical communities, public health officials, researchers, practitioners, and child advocates. Since members of these various fields tend to use their own definitions, communication across disciplines can be limited, hampering efforts to identify, assess, track, treat, and prevent child maltreatment.

Introduction:

The term child abuse is often interchangeably, although some researchers make a distinction between them, treating to cover neglect, exploitation, and trafficking. In this study it is helpful to control all the problems which is faced by the children in our society. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines child abuse and child maltreatment as "all forms of physical and/or emotional ill-treatment, sexual abuse, neglect or negligent treatment or commercial or other exploitation, resulting in actual or potential harm to the child's health, survival, development or dignity in the context of a relationship of responsibility, trust or power." Child abuse isn't just about black eyes. While physical abuse is shocking due to the marks it leaves, not all signs of child abuse are as obvious. Ignoring children's needs, putting them in unsupervised, dangerous situations, exposing them to sexual situations, or making them feel worthless or stupid are also forms of child abuse and neglect and they can leave deep, lasting scars on kids. All types of abuse and neglect leave lasting scars. Some of these scars might be physical, but emotional scarring has long lasting effects throughout life, damaging a child's sense of self, their future relationships, and ability to function at home, work and school. 53% of children in India face some form of child abuse. According to the National Crime Records Bureau, the cases of rape and murder of children increase every year. The growing complexities of life and the changed social economic conditions have exposed the children to new and different forms of abuse. But the sad state of the affairs is that such heinous acts are reported less. It has such a psychological impact on the mind of the child that he/she seldom gathers the courage to speak about the act being committed against him/her. If even if he confides the fact with someone, the social factors let the fact being dumped under the fear of family reputation and

Literature Review:

Katherine McArthur (2009): This study results in the research about child abuse, child protection and disabled children are also leading to a child abuse. This review was conducted using five stages. This study revealed a disability and child maltreatment, the evidence shows that the interaction of age, gender and socio factors. This case also revealed the study about, disabled children are also associated in child abuse. Very few studies have sought disabled children's own accounts of abuse or safeguarding. Considerable development is required, at both policy and practice level, to ensure that disabled children's right to protection is upheld. The paper concludes by identifying a number of aspects of the topic requiring further investigation.

Galleger B (1999): In this study, acknowledged that a second feature of the literature has been its concentration upon sexual abuse. They have taken the cases of child abuse last ten years and reviewed about the particular cases. This study also explains that child is abused with the substance, physically, mentally and emotionally. So that children can get depressed and even leads to suicidal thoughts. So that, they have reviewed about, that child can be safe and secure only when they have family support and safety measures and precautions were explained in this study.

Clare Mariotte (2013): The review research investigating about the outcomes for people with a history of childhood sexual abuse and implications for practice, as well as to consider issues for clearer definitions. The reviewed papers identified a number of factors that were repeatedly associated with individuals showing the frequent sexual abuse outcomes. These included inner resources coping skills, interpretation of experiences and self-esteem, family relationships, friendships, community resources as well as some abuse-related factors. A

large number of methodological concerns within these studies were also noted, including the way in which resilience, CSA and protective factors were defined. However, despite this, many papers identified similar factors that could be utilized to develop both effective prevention programme and resilience interventions for the survivors of CSA.

Reena R (2008): This article reviews explains about the study of sexual abuse education and/or body safety programme, as well as the research surrounding them. Advantages as well as criticisms of such programme are reviewed. Issues such as target populations (i.e. children, teachers, parents), Major findings include: children as young as three can be effectively taught self-protection skills, parental and family involvement in training is important, and repeated exposure helps children maintain knowledge gains. The components of successful programme include teaching children to identify and resist inappropriate touching, reassuring children that it is not their fault and learning the proper names of their genitals. Finally, future directions for programme development, research and policy are explored.

Zuravin, Susan J: This report explains about the current knowledge about the ecological determinants of child maltreatment and maltreatment rates. A review of these findings revealed literature in the early stages of development. The ecology of sexual abuse, and studies of physical abuse and neglect are demonstrated by the abuse evidence. Study findings reveal that five of the seven are independent correlates of neglect, and four are correlates of abuse; it also happens by the inadequate social support indicators.

About Our Study: In this study we have taken a survey about the causes for the child abuse, when, where, how the child gets abused and what kind of punishment can be given to those victims etc., we took a survey based on the child abuse in which the child gets affected whether by substance, emotionally or physically. It can helpful to view clearly about the status of child abuse and how many of them were accept and refuse the questions which we have given in the survey to fill by the people. It also keenly focuses on the awareness which is created in our society based on the child abuse.

Objectives:

- Perspective of child abuse based on the gender and age ii. Creating an awareness over the child abuse
- Awareness over the substance abuse, physical abuse, sexual abuse etc., iv. Making the female more cautious by this study
- To create a support programme over the society

Research Methodology:

Survey Method:

Survey method was being used to collect data from the respondent. In this technique data is collected by asking questions to people about the abuse and its awareness. For this purpose, a formal list of questionnaires is been prepared and circulated.

Data Collection:

Design Source:

Primary Data:

In this research the data are being collected in and around the Tamil Nadu, during the Period February to March 2020. For this purpose, people were categorized based on age and gender. They were asked to respond for the questionnaire prepared.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data refers to the information which is present in the earlier resources. The secondary data is collected from

- Reports and Records
- Websites
- Books
- Journals

Using IBM SPSS software tools, the data were analyzed. The collected data were analyzed using one-way Anova test, Pearson Correlation, cross tabulation, descriptive statistics. IBM SPSS software is a platform that offers advanced statistical analysis, library of machine learning algorithms, test analysis, open-source extensibility, and integration with big data. It is used to improve efficiency and minimize risk. In this research model we use IBM SPSS Statistics 23.

Anova:

One-way analysis of variance is the technique that is used to compare the means of two or more samples. The significant value is 0.05. if the p value is less than 0.05 then the null hypothesis is rejected else it is accepted.

Correlation:

The person correlation of the bivariate correlation is the measure of linear correlation between two variables. The test of significance one tail is selected based on the variable. Hypothesis of the significance test for correlation can be expressed depending on one tail or two tail tests.

Cross Tabulation:

Cross tabulation is used to examine relationships within data that may not be readily apparent. Cross tabulation is especially useful for studying market research or survey responses.

Frequency Analysis:

Frequency Analysis is a part of descriptive statistics, frequency is the number of times an event occurs. Frequency Analysis is an important area of statistics that deals with the number of occurrences.

Sample Size:

To conduct this research nearly 100 respondents who are categorized based on age and gender asked to respond for questionnaire given.

Analysis Methods:

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12	Q13	Q14	Q15
N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Mean	4.01	3.03	3.96	2.76	3.81	3.82	3.59	3.13	2.63	3.36	3.56	2.48	4.27	4.33	2.45
Sum	401	303	396	276	381	382	359	313	263	336	356	248	427	433	245

Table 1

Interpretation:

The table shows the various mean for the survey collected. As the rating for the rated between 1 to 5. The average mean is 3. Comparing all the mean, Q12 & Q15 varies a lot from the average mean 3.

Analysis Based on Age:

Age	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
19	4	4	4
20	14	14	18
21	15	15	33
22	21	21	54
23	24	24	78
24	10	10	88
25	1	1	89
26	2	2	91
27	1	1	92
29	1	1	93
32	1	1	94
37	1	1	95
39	2	2	97
43	1	1	98
50	1	1	99
52	1	1	100
Total	100	100	

Table 2

Interpretation:

The table shows frequency analysis based on age. The age varies between 19 to 52. The highest range of responses comes from the age 20 to 24. The minimum number of responses ranges between 19, 25 to 52.

Analysis Based on Gender:

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	60	60	60	60
Male	40	40	40	40
Total	100	100	100	100

Table 3

Interpretation:

The table shows frequency analysis based on age. Total number of samples collected is 100. From the above table, it can be known that total number of female and male responses are 60 and 50.

Analysis for Relationship between Gender and Questionnaire:

Group Statistics	Gender	N	Mean	F	P value
Cumulative of Q1 to Q13	Female	60	40.48	0.551	0.46
	Male	40	39.63		

Table 4

Interpretation:

The above table is derived using T-test. Null hypothesis is equal to there is no significant difference between the cumulative of Q1 to Q13 and gender. The P value is 0.460. If $P > 0.05$ (accept null hypothesis) and if $P < 0.05$ (reject null hypothesis).

Thus, the P value calculated > 0.05 , therefore accept the null hypothesis. It can be concluded that there is relation between the gender and the cumulative of Q1 to Q13 (questionnaires).

Analysis Based on Q1 Questionnaire:

Some children are sexually abused by older people?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
Some children are sexually abused by older people?	Strongly Disagree	1	1	3	5	2	3
	Disagree	0	2	0	2	0	2
	I don't know	2	7	1	10	5	5
	Agree	8	39	6	53	33	20
	Strongly Agree	7	21	2	30	20	10
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 4

Interpretation:

According to age, 53% of the people agree that children are abused by older people. According to gender, 33% of female agree it.

Analysis Based on Q2 Questionnaire:

Most people who sexually abuse children do not belong to the child family?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
Most people who sexually abuse children do not belong to the child family	Strongly Disagree	0	3	4	7	1	6
	Disagree	4	21	5	30	23	7
	I don't know	5	19	0	24	13	11
	Agree	8	21	2	31	19	12
	Strongly Agree	1	6	1	8	4	4
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 5

Interpretation:

According to age, 31% of the people agree that the most people who sexually abusing children were not belong to child family. According to gender, 23% of the female disagree with this statement.

Analysis Based on Q3 Questionnaire:

Most of the time children are sexually abused when they are alone at night and outside their home?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
Most of the time children are sexually abused when they are alone at night and outside their home?	Strongly Disagree	0	4	3	7	1	6
	Disagree	0	6	1	7	23	7
	I don't know	2	2	2	6	13	11
	Agree	7	31	5	43	19	12
	Strongly Agree	9	27	1	37	4	4
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 6

Interpretation:

According to age, 43% of the people agreed that most of the children were abused when they are alone at night and outside their home. According to gender, 23% of the female disagree.

Analysis Based on Q4 Questionnaire:

Only young children are victims of sexual Abuse?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
Only young children are victims of sexual Abuse?	Strongly Disagree	2	9	4	15	9	6
	Disagree	4	29	6	39	24	15
	I don't know	2	11	1	14	7	7
	Agree	6	12	1	19	11	8
	Strongly Agree	4	9	0	13	9	4
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 7

Interpretation:

According to age, 39% of the people disagree that only young children gets abused. According to gender, majorly it is disagreed by female.

Analysis Based on Q5 Questionnaire:

Do you think you know about child abuse and its influence on a child?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
Do you think you know about child abuse and its influence on a child?	Strongly Disagree	1	7	3	11	6	5
	Disagree	4	9	2	15	11	4
	Agree	10	43	3	56	31	25
	Strongly Agree	3	11	4	18	12	6
Total		18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 8

Interpretation:

According to age, 56% of the people agreed that the people know about the child abuse and its influence on a child. According to gender, 31% female agree with this.

Analysis Based on Q6 Questionnaire:

In sexual Abuse cases, the child him/ herself is never responsible*

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
In sexual Abuse cases, the child him/ herself is never responsible *	Strongly Disagree	0	3	0	3	1	2
	Disagree	3	6	2	11	9	2
	I don't know	4	12	1	17	9	8
	Agree	7	28	4	39	25	14
	Strongly Agree	4	21	5	30	16	14
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 9

Interpretation:

According to age, 39% of the people agreed that the child is not never responsible for the sexual abuse. According to gender, 25% female agree with the statement.

Analysis Based on Q7 Questionnaire:

Have you ever tried to teach a child about Abuse and good/bad touch?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
Have you ever tried to teach a child about Abuse and good/bad touch?	Strongly Disagree	1	0	0	1	1	0
	Disagree	0	6	3	9	7	2
	I don't know	5	26	3	34	15	19
	Agree	9	29	4	42	29	13
	Strongly Agree	3	9	2	14	8	6
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 10

Interpretation:

According to age, 42% of the people agree that people were tried to teach about the child about abuse and good and bad touch. According to gender, 29% female have tried to teach about the abuse and good/bad touch.

Analysis Based on Q8 Questionnaire:

A majority of sexual Abuse perpetrators are retarded or mentally ill

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
A majority of sexual Abuse perpetrators are retarded or mentally ill?	Strongly Disagree	1	3	0	4	3	1
	Disagree	3	19	7	29	18	11
	I don't know	5	20	0	25	16	9
	Agree	7	23	4	34	17	17
	Strongly Agree	2	5	1	8	6	2
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 11

Interpretation:

According to age, most of the people agreed that the majority of sexual abuse perpetrators are retarded or mentally ill. According to gender, 18% of the female disagree with the statement.

Analysis Based on Q9 Questionnaire:

Do you think there is less awareness regarding the child abuse?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
Do you think there is less awareness regarding the child abuse?	Strongly Disagree	3	6	1	10	3	1
	Disagree	3	29	7	39	18	11
	I don't know	8	22	2	32	16	9
	Agree	3	11	2	16	17	17
	Strongly Agree	1	2	0	3	6	2
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 12

Interpretation:

According to age, 39% of the people disagree that there is less awareness regarding the child abuse. According to gender, 18% of the female disagree with the statement.

Analysis Based on Q10 Questionnaire:

Do you see any suspicious case of child abuse frequently?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
Do you see any suspicious case of child abuse frequently?	Strongly Disagree	1	3	0	4	1	3
	Disagree	4	21	2	27	17	10
	I don't know	3	9	4	16	12	4
	Agree	7	25	3	35	18	17
	Strongly Agree	3	12	3	18	12	6
Total	18	70	12	100	60	40	

Table 13

Interpretation:

According to age, 35% of the people agree that most of them seeing the suspicious case of child abuse frequently. According to gender, 18% of the female agree with the statement.

Analysis Based on Q11 Questionnaire:

It is the technology which is influencing these types of crime to happen?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
It is the technology which is influencing these types of crime to happen	Strongly Disagree	0	2	0	2	1	1
	Disagree	1	15	1	17	9	8
	I don't know	4	12	2	18	9	9
	Agree	11	29	9	49	32	17
	Strongly Agree	2	12	0	14	9	5
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 14

Interpretation:

According to age, 49% of the people agree that it is a technology which influencing these types of crime to happen. According to gender, 32% of the female agree with the statement.

Analysis Based on Q12 Questionnaire:

Boys are not sexually abused?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
Boys are not sexually abused?	Strongly Disagree	2	18	7	27	10	17
	Disagree	6	18	3	27	22	5
	I don't know	4	19	0	23	17	6
	Agree	5	11	1	17	7	10
	Strongly Agree	1	4	1	6	4	2
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 15

Interpretation:

According to age, 27% of the people disagreed and strongly disagreed that the boys are not sexually abused. According to gender, 22% of female disagree with statement.

Analysis Based on Q13 Questionnaire:

To your opinion, which type of child abuse is to be issue to be taken into consideration?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male

To your opinion, which type of child abuse is to be concerned or issue to be taken into consideration	Strongly Disagree	1	2	0	3	3	0
	Disagree	4	12	0	16	6	10
	I don't know	2	2	2	6	4	2
	Agree	0	1	0	1	0	1
	Strongly Agree	11	53	10	74	47	27
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 16

Interpretation:

According to age, 74% of the people strongly agreed that these types of child abuse should be concerned or issues to be taken into consideration

Analysis Based on Q14 Questionnaire:

To your opinion, what is the reason for child abuse?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
To your opinion, what is the reason for child abuse	Porn Videos	2	7	0	9	5	4
	No Moral Support to Victim	0	4	0	4	3	1
	Lack of Human Values	3	15	5	23	12	11
	Other	13	44	7	64	40	24
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 17

Interpretation:

According to age, 64% of the people said other for the questionnaire, what is the reason for child abuse. According to gender, 40% of female and 24% of male responded with varies opinions.

Analysis Based on Q15 Questionnaire:

What would be your suggestions to overcome the child abuse?

		Age3			Total	Gender	
		<20	20-25	>25		Female	Male
What would be your suggestions to overcome the child abuse	bring new law with brutal punishment	8	20	3	31	23	8
	the culprit should be punished on spot by the public too	8	31	2	41	22	19
	educate people with human values	2	5	1	8	4	4
	other	0	14	6	20	11	9
	Total	18	70	12	100	60	40

Table 18

Interpretation:

According to age, 41% of the people answered that the culprit should be punished on spot by the public. According to gender, 23% of female believe that those culprits should be brutally punished.

Findings, Recommendation & Conclusion:

Findings:

- Among 100 respondents
- The survey collected provides different opinion based on age and gender.
- According to age category, 60 female respondent and 40 male respondents.
- Below 20 age category, 18 respondents are found.
- 20 to 25 age category, 70 respondents are found.
- Greater than 25, 12 respondents are found.
- Comparing all the question, Q12 and Q15 have major different respondent compare to other questions
- The age varies between 19 to 52. The highest range of responses comes from the age 20 to 24.
- The minimum number of responses ranges between 19, 25 to 52.
- Total number of samples collected is 100.
- The P value is 0.460. If $P > 0.05$ (accept null hypothesis) and if $P < 0.05$ (reject null hypothesis).
- According to age, 53%of the people agree that children are abused by older people. According to gender, 33% of female agree it.
- According to age, 31% of the people agree that the most people who sexually abusing children were not belong to child family. According to gender, 23% of the female disagree it

- According to age, 43% of the people agreed that most of the children were abused when they are alone at night and outside their home. According to gender, 23% of the female disagree it.
- According to age, 43% of the people agreed that most of the children were abused when they are alone at night and outside their home. According to gender, 23% of the female disagree it.
- According to age, 56% of the people agreed that the people know about the child abuse and its influence on a child. According to gender, 31% female agree with this.
- According to age, 39% of the people agreed that the child is not never responsible for the sexual abuse. According to gender, 25% female agree it.
- According to age, 42% of the people agree that people were tried to teach about the child about abuse and good and bad touch. According to gender, 29% female have tried to teach about the abuse and good/bad touch.
- According to age, most of the people agreed that the majority of sexual abuse perpetrators are retarded or mentally ill. According to gender, 18% of the female disagree it.
- According to age, 39% of the people disagree that there is less awareness regarding the child abuse. According to gender, 18% of the female disagree with the statement.
- According to age, 35% of the people agree that most of them seeing the suspicious case of child abuse frequently. According to gender, 18% of the female agree it.
- According to age, 49% of the people agree that it is a technology which influencing these types of crime to happen. According to gender, 32% of the female agree it.
- According to age, 27% of the people disagreed and strongly disagreed that the boys are not sexually abused. According to gender, 22% of female disagree with statement.
- According to age, 74% of the people strongly agreed that these types of child abuse should be concerned or issues to be taken into consideration
- According to age, 64% of the people said other for the questionnaire, what is the reason for child abuse. According to gender, 40% of female and 24% of male responded with varies opinions.
- According to age, 41% of the people answered that the culprit should be punished on spot by the public. According to gender, 23% of female believe that those culprits should be brutally punished.

Recommendations:

- From the research, it is found that most of the respondents are female, but there are few differentiations in response about the awareness. Few responses were similar between the female and male. Majority of the people were aware about the abuse. As the child abuse is a severe crime there should be some lawful punishment with the brutal action should be given to the culprit. According to age, 70% of the respondents were between 21 to 25 which shows that the growing generation is aware about the issue. This age group people should create more awareness among the future generation about this abuse as they are in first stage of making family. Kids should be taught about the good touch and bad touch. They should not hesitate to talk about this severe abuse to the kids, because this is the stage where, the mistakes start. It means, when these kids grow up, they should not be a part of child abuse as victim as well as culprit. It is recommended to educate the school teachers as the kids spend most of the time in schools. It is highly recommended that kids below the age of seven should not be left alone at anytime, anywhere and for anything.
- It would be good if the kids are thought about this abuse priorly even when they are able to understand very little things. The parents are the one who should be highly aware about the crime. There are many uneducated parents too, the schools can take an initiative step towards this and teach the parents about the abuse which would be very helpful. Every kid across the globe is a gift from god. It is our responsibility to take care to look after them, to teach them, to groom them, to encourage them, to fight against the fear and to protect them but not to spoil them.
- They should be given freedom to talk about their emotional needs. A kid should be encouraged to come up the difficulty they face. If the child abuse and neglect issues affect the kid negatively may cause severe injury to the kid both mentally and physically. If a kid is abused in any form, physical, sexual, substance, mentally, emotionally. If the kid is abused kindly find it out as soon as possible to save the kid.

Conclusion:

From the research on child abuse, it is known that even male child is abused. Research indicates that all types of abuse have to be taken into consideration. The study provide evidence for the existence of child abuse in all forms. This study suggest that child abuse have serious effects on adolescent mental health. High stakes are involved in believing or disbelieving as a child assertion that they have been abused by adults. Although relevant study do not always address directly the coaching of children, they support a conclusion that other types of false abuse allegations by children are uncommon. Exposure to abuse appears to increase risk of involvement

in violent behaviour and alcohol abuse. It can be concluded that the recommendations can be followed to overcome the issue.

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